

Software Development Technology Productivity – Experiment protocol – part II (software application maintenance)

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1. Introduction

The project's second stage arises from the need to make functional changes in the system, translated into corrective maintenance and evolutionary maintenance.

This new version will primarily focus on tasks and recorded data. Specifically:

- The previously defined "EndDate" field of the "Task" table (in Part I of the protocol) should be changed to "ExpectedEndDate" (deadline). In addition, a new attribute named "ActualEndDate" must also be added to this table. Finally, there should also be the possibility of adding more than one collaborator to each task, so that the task can be performed by several collaborators, contrarily to the previous version, which had the business rule “a task is executed by one and only one collaborator”.
- Focusing on the details of the project, a new tab should be created, called "Indicators", enabling the project manager to obtain an overview of the tasks' status. The collaborators should also have a new tab named "Performance" available in the top menu to allow them to get an overview of the tasks they are involved in.

2. Functional Model

The software consists of three modules (packages), as depicted in Figure 1: Authentication (P1); User Management (P2); Project and Task Management (P3).

In this new version, there are no changes to the Authentication Module or to the User Management Module.

Figure 1. Packages

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Figure 2 shows the use cases of the *Project and Task Management* module (package P3).

Figure 2. Use case diagram – Project and Task Management (P3)

3. Use Case Specifications

3.1. Create Project Task (UC3.6)

To access the “Create Task” functionality, the user must click on the respective button at the upper right corner of the “Task List” page (see Figure 15 in Protocol I). They will then be redirected to a form that allows the creation of tasks (Figure 3). This form contains several fields, namely code, name, status (“Not Started”, “In progress”, “Pending” and “Complete”), a brief description, the start date and expected end date, the actual end date of the task, and the estimated and actual effort in executing the task (in minutes). Some of the values of these fields — such as, for instance, the task’s status — will be updated during the task’s execution. Additionally, it is possible to assign collaborators to the task by selecting a collaborator and clicking on the “Assign” button. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 1.

The screenshot shows a web interface for creating a task. The top navigation bar includes 'Easy Management', 'Projects', 'Tasks', and 'Users'. The main content area is titled 'Project 1' and has three tabs: 'Informations', 'Tasks', and 'Collaborators'. The 'Tasks' tab is selected. The 'Create Task' form contains the following fields and elements:

- Code:** Text input field.
- Name:** Text input field.
- Status:** Dropdown menu.
- Description:** Text area.
- Start Date:** Date picker.
- Expected End Date:** Date picker.
- Actual End Date:** Date picker.
- Estimated Effort (Minutes):** Text input field.
- Actual Effort (Minutes):** Text input field.

On the left, under 'My Projects', there are three checkboxes: 'Project 1' (checked), 'Project 2', and 'Project 3'. On the right, there is a 'Collaborator' dropdown menu and an 'Assign' button. Below the dropdown, there are three rows for collaborators: 'User 1' (Manager), 'User 2' (Collaborator), and 'User 3' (Collaborator), each with an 'Unassign' button. At the bottom, there are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 3. Create Project Task

Table 1. Create Project Task

UC3.6	Create Project Task
Description: This use case allows creating a task associated with a particular project.	
Pre-Conditions: The user must be authenticated and have Project Manager permission.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user click on the “Create Task” button. 2. A form is displayed for the user to fill in. 3. The user fills in and submits the form. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative Flows: A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form is closed and the “Project (Tasks tab)” page is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors found when filling in the form. 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: A new task is saved. The page “Project (Tasks tab)” is displayed.	

3.2. Edit Project Task (UC3.9)

To access the “Edit Task” functionality, the user must click on a task in the list of tasks, and will then be redirected to the task viewing/editing page (Figure 4). After changing the fields, the user should click on the “Save” button to submit the changes. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 2.

The screenshot displays the 'Easy Management' web application interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Projects', 'Tasks', and 'Users'. The main content area is titled 'Project 1' and features three tabs: 'Informations', 'Tasks', and 'Collaborators'. The 'Tasks' tab is active, showing an 'Edit Task' form. On the left, a 'My Projects' section lists 'Project 1' (checked), 'Project 2', and 'Project 3'. The 'Edit Task' form includes fields for Code, Name, Status, Description, Start Date, Expected End Date, Actual End Date, Estimated Effort (Minutes), and Actual Effort (Minutes). A 'Collaborator' dropdown menu is set to 'User 1' (Manager), with an 'Assign' button and a trash icon. Below this, a table lists 'User 2' (Collaborator) and 'User 3' (Collaborator), each with an 'Unassign' button. At the bottom of the form are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 4. Edit Project Task

Table 2. Edit Project Task

UC3.9	Edit Project Task
Description: The use case allows editing a task associated with a project.	
Pre-Conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user selects from the task list the task they want to edit. 2. A form is displayed with the task details. 3. The user fills in and submits the form. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. A2. The form has errors. 	
Alternative Flows: A1. The user clicks on the “Cancel” button. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The form is closed and the “Project (Tasks tab)” page is displayed (without saving the form data). - A2. The form has errors. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A message is displayed identifying the errors found when filling in the form (e.g., “code not filled in”, “code already exists”, “name not filled in”, “name already exists”). All fields are mandatory, except the description, actual effort, and collaborators. 2. The flow returns to step 3 of the Main Flow. 	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: The task data is updated. The page “Project (Tasks tab)” is displayed.	

3.3. View Collaborator Indicators (UC3.11)

To access the collaborator's indicators, the user must click on the "Indicators" tab on the top menu. Then they will be redirected to the page where their indicators are displayed (Figure 5). The use case specification is shown in Table 3.

Figure 5. View Collaborator Indicators

Table 3. View Collaborator Indicators

UC3.11	View Collaborator Indicators
Description: This use case allows consulting the indicators of a collaborator.	
Pre-Conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: 1. The user accesses the "Indicators" tab. 2. The indicators about their tasks' status are displayed.	
Alternative Flows: -	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

3.4. View Project Indicators (UC3.12)

To access the page of project indicators (see Figure 6), the user must first access the page listing the projects and select the project. After that, the user must click on the tab "Indicators", where the indicators of the selected project are displayed. The specification of the use case is shown in Table 4.

Figure 6. View Project Indicators

Table 4. View Project Indicators

UC3.12	View Project Indicators
Description: This use case allows consulting the indicators of a project.	
Pre-Conditions: The user must be authenticated.	
Main Flow: 1. The user accesses the "Indicators" tab. 2. The project indicators regarding tasks' status are displayed.	
Alternative Flows: -	
Exceptions: -	
Post-Conditions: -	

4. Structural Model (Data Model) - Update

The entity and relationship diagram illustrates the entities relevant to the application and how they relate to each other. As shown in Figure 7, there are seven entities. In comparison with the model of protocol I, this time was added the entity Project_User_Task, which relates the entities Project_User and Task. Two new attributes were also added to the Task entity, named "ExpectedEndDate" and "ActualEndDate", and the attribute "EndDate" was removed.

The following business rule was also added: a task is executed by one or more collaborators.

Figure 7. Entity-Relationship Model